

D4.2 First report on intelligent nApps and 5G-IANA UCs development

Dissemination level:	Public (PU)
Work package:	WP4
Task:	T4.3: Intelligent nApps and 5G-IANA UCs
Deliverable lead:	HYP
Version:	V2.6
Submission date:	11/07/2023
Due date:	30/06/2023
Partners:	

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101016427

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Control sheet

Version history			
Version	Date	Modified by	Summary of changes
v0.1	12/04/2023	Marios Zinonos	ToC, Initial Chapters
V0.2	02/05/2023	Anastasis Sinanis	Added specification example on chapter 2.1.1, table 1
V0.3	20/06/2023	Anastasis Sinanis	Restructured document, now AF/NF are described in chapter 2 and nApps at chapter 3
V0.4	20/06/2023	Matteo Andolfi	Input in chapters 4.2, 4.3
V0.5	20/06/2023	Anastasis Sinanis	Introduction + section 4 & input of 4.1
V0.6	21/06/2023	Anastasis Sinanis	Edited presentation template per UC
V0.7	22/06/2023	Anastasis Sinanis	1) Input Section 2.1, 2) Added partner contribution (BYL) in section 2.3, 3) Updated UC3 in section 2.4
V0.8	27/06/2023	Anastasis Sinanis	1) Added section 3.4., 2) Incorporated contribution from the following partners ININ, UULM, O7, 5COMM
V0.9	28/06/2023	Anastasis Sinanis	Edited fonts, table & figure numbering
V1.0	28/06/2023	Anastasis Sinanis	1) Incorporated contribution from the following partners: COGN,

			2) Added executive summary & Conclusion
V2.0	30/06/2023	Anastasis Sinanis	Draft ready for peer review
V2.1	04/07/2023	Yann Garcia	Peer reviewed document
V2.2	05/07/2023	Jose Isola	Peer reviewed document
V2.5	06/07/2023	Anastasis Sinanis	Modifications after peer review
V2.6	10/07/2023	Eirini Liotou	Final Quality check

Peer review		
	Reviewer name	Date
Reviewer 1	Yann Garcia (FSCOM)	03-Jul-2023
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ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
5G-IANA	5G Intelligent Automotive Network Applications
5G-PPP	5G Public Private Partnership
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AF	Application Function
AGV	Automated Guided Vehicle
AOEP	Automotive Open Experimental Platform
API	Application Programming Interface
AR	Augmented Reality
AV	Autonomous Vehicle
CI	Continuous Integration
C-ITS	Cooperative Intelligent Transport Systems
CPM	Collective Perception Message
CPU	Central Processing Unit
DL	Downlink
DML	Distributed Machine Learning
E2E	End-to-End
FOV	Field-of-View
GPS	Global Positioning System
HMD	Head Mounted Display
HMI	Human-Machine Interface
ITS	Intelligent Transportation System
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LDM	Local Dynamic Map
MANO	Management and Orchestration
MCAD	Manoeuvre Coordination for Autonomous Driving

ML	Machine Learning
NF	Network Function
NFV	Network Functions Virtualisation
NW	Network
OS	Operating System
PQoS	Predictive Quality of Services
PU	Public
OBU	On-Board Unit
QoE	Quality of Experience
QoS	Quality of Service
RAN	Radio Access Network
RTT	Round-Trip-Time
SME	Small and Medium Sized Enterprise(s)
UC	Use Case
UDP	User Datagram Protocol
UE	User Equipment
UHD	Ultra-High Definition
UL	Uplink
UPF	User Plane Function
VAO	Vertical Application Orchestrator
VBT	Virtual Bus Tour
vOBU	Virtual On-Board Unit
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

The present document titled “D4.2: First report on Intelligent nApps and 5G-IANA UCs development” has been developed under task T4.2, focused on the “Intelligent nApps and 5G-IANA UCs”. The primary objective of this deliverable is to provide an initial overview of the development of network applications (nApps) and Use Cases (UCs) that is unfolded within Work Package (WP) 4 “5G-IANA nApps toolkit development”. These applications and use cases will be offered as vertical services on the 5G-IANA Automotive Open Experimental Platform (AOEP).

The AOEP vertical services are comprised of two main building blocks, the atomic components, which include Application and Network Functions (AFs/NFs), and the nApps, which are created by interconnecting AFs/NFs. The components used in the 5G-IANA platform were defined in D4.1, while D7.7 reported the related IPR information of these components (AFs/NFs).

This document presents a total of 25 nApps, out of which 23 have been identified within the scope of UC service chain composition. Additionally, the ITS communication and video processing nApp, developed by LINKS, serves as a core building block for building Automotive Vertical services. Furthermore, the document provides examples of vertical service composition utilizing the supplied atomic components.

The document provides information on the end-to-end (E2E) service chain composition and defines the atomic components that constitute the UCs. It also includes an update on the current development status for Cycle A (M12-M25). Furthermore, D4.2 depicts a presentation template used for AFs/NFs, mapping each field to the GUI and the information model fields. This template serves as a reference point for UC developers and third-party experimenters using the 5G-IANA platform. Additionally, the document presents a categorization of the UC-defined nApps in relation to other vertical services.

Following the development of an nApp, the next step is to make it available as a containerized component on the AOEP by adding the container image to the 5G-IANA catalogue. This process involves the onboarding process on the AOEP, which will be facilitated using the nApp starter kit. The present document describes the overall process, including details of the API used for onboarding. Furthermore, D4.2 includes results of a literature review on methods employed by other 5G-related ICT-41 projects for storing, deploying, and providing vertical services, in comparison with the 5G-IANA decisions. Several projects have implemented different methods for nApp repositories such as Smart5Grid, VITAL-5G, 5G Induce, 5G-MEDIA HUB, 5GASP, EVOLVED-5G, and

5G-Epicentre. Regarding the common approaches for integrating nApps into vertical services, three categories are identified: the coupled or delegated approach, the As-a-Service approach, and the Hybrid approach. The As-a-Service approach is the most used category, followed by the Hybrid approach in H2020 research projects.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. 5G-IANA concept and approach

5G-IANA aims at providing an open 5G experimentation platform, on top of which third-party experimenters, i.e., SMEs in the Automotive vertical sector will have the opportunity to develop, deploy and test their services. The provided Automotive Open Experimentation Platform (AOEP) is a set of hardware and software resources that provides the computational and communication/transport infrastructure as well as the management and orchestration components, coupled with an enhanced nApp Toolkit tailored to the Automotive sector, for simplifying the design and onboarding of new nApps. 5G-IANA exposes to experimenters secured and standardized Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) for facilitating all the different steps towards the production stage of a new service. 5G-IANA targets different virtualization technologies integrating different Management and Orchestration (MANO) frameworks for enabling the deployment of end-to-end network services across different segments (vehicles, road infrastructure, Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) nodes and cloud resources). 5G-IANA nApp toolkit is linked with an Automotive Network Functions (NFs) Repository including an extensive portfolio of ready-to-use and openly accessible Automotive-related NFs and nApp templates, that are available for SMEs to use and develop new applications. Finally, 5G-IANA develops a Distributed Machine Learning (DML) framework, that provides functionalities for simplified management and orchestration of collections of Machine Learning (ML) service components and thus, allows ML-based applications to penetrate the Automotive world, due to its inherent privacy-preserving nature. 5G-IANA will be demonstrated through seven Automotive-related use cases in two 5G Stand Alone (SA) testbeds. Moving beyond technological challenges, and exploiting input from the demonstration activities, 5G-IANA will identify and validate market conditions for innovative, yet sustainable business models for the AOEP platform, supporting a long-term roadmap towards the pan-European deployment of 5G as a key advanced Automotive services enabler.

1.2. Purpose of the deliverable

The purpose of this deliverable is to report the progress on the development of the intelligent nApps and the 5G-IANA UCs. Section 22.3 focuses on the AF and NF development status, while also presenting the interfaces that will be used by the NFs and AFs developed in each UC and a first version of the validation scenarios.

Section 3 presents a listing of the nApps offered by each UC while additional examples on how these nApps can be utilized by third-party experimenters to create new or enhanced ones, are presented in Section 3.3.

Finally, in Section 4, a brief overview of how other similar projects handle nApp storage, usage and deployment is given. This is followed by 5G-IANA specifics on the AOEP onboarding process and the onboarding REST API in Sections 4.2 and 4.3.

1.3. Intended audience

The dissemination level of this deliverable is “public” (PU)¹. It is primarily aimed to be the reference document to be used by the 5G-IANA Consortium Members during the development and integration phases of the atomic components and nApps of the 5G-IANA project. Moreover, it will be a useful document (“manual”) for the third-parties, i.e., SMEs, who will experiment on the 5G-IANA platform during the project’s Open Calls, in the sense that it is the first public document of the project that contains a full list of the nApps offered by the project and the components that form them.

¹ REMARK: D4.2 1 is tagged as Confidential in the DoW. It will be changed to Public following an Amendment.

2. APPLICATION AND NETWORK FUNCTIONS DEVELOPMENT

An overview of the atomic components and the network services composed by these components (nApps) per UC will be presented in this section. Moreover, the present section describes the development progress, and crucial information, such as the initial defined interfaces, resource requirements and configuration options, as well as the deployment location of the atomic components.

2.1. 5G-IANA platform template mapping between D4.2 and Vertical App Composition and Customization

This chapter focuses on the mapping between the AF/NF template used in the 5G-IANA platform and the Vertical App Composition and Customization. The AF/NF template contains various information related to the 5G-IANA Graphical User Interface (GUI) and its underlying information model. It also includes higher-level details such as the AF/NF description in relation to the Use Case (UC) where it is utilized, deployment notes, and data format.

The purpose of this mapping is to establish a connection between the AF/NF template and the information model GUI of 5G-IANA, as well as the Vertical App Composition and Customization. This enables better understanding and integration of the AF/NF components within the overall platform architecture. To facilitate this mapping, Table 1 outlines the specific items in the AF/NF template and their corresponding fields in the Information Model GUI. The table includes:

- The defined name of the AF/NF, mapped to the Atomic Component information model in the GUI.
- The latest version of the AF/NF.
- A high-level description of the AF/NF's utility and its role in the service chain.
- Information about the domains where the AF/NF will be deployed in relation to the UC.
- The minimum resources needed for the AF/NF execution, including any GPU requirements.
- The ports exposed during the dockerization of the AF/NF, mapped to the Exported Interface information model.
- The network protocol used to receive input (Expected input).

- The network protocol utilized for providing output (Expected output).
- Any configuration options, if applicable.
- Specific notes related to deployment scenarios or network data format used for input/output.
- The development status of the AFs/NFs.

It should be noted that this mapping is being investigated to establish a clear correspondence between the AF/NF template and the Vertical Application Orchestrator (VAO) component. The purpose is to ensure seamless integration and effective orchestration of vertical applications within the 5G-IANA platform.

Table 1: AF/NF Template mapping to 5G-IANA Information model GUI

Specification Item	Description	Mapping to Information Model field	Mapping to Vertical App Composition and Customization field
Name	AF/NF defined name	Atomic Component information model → name	GUI: Components → General → Name (Figure 1)
Version	Latest version of the AF/NF	<i>No direct linkage</i> Refers to the Atomic Component information model → docker Image	<i>No direct linkage</i> Refers to the docker image version
Description	A high-level description of the utility of the atomic component, as well as its utility in the service chain	N/A	N/A
Deployment	The domains where this AF/NF will be deployed in regards to the UC Notation: 'EDGE Server + OBU': the AF/NF will be deployed across both domains 'EDGE Server, OBU': the AF/NF can be deployed in both domains	Exported Interface information model → interface Type metadata	GUI: Components → General <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Select Region dropdown menu (Figure 6) • Select Node dropdown menu (Figure 7)
Required Resources	The minimum required resources required for the execution of this AF/NF. GPU requirement is described in this field	Requirement information model	GUI: Components → Minimum Execution Requirements (Figure 5)

Exposed ports	The ports that are exposed during the dockerization of this atomic component	Exported Interface information model → Port	Exposed Interfaces → Interface creation menu → Port (Figure 4)
Expected Input	The network protocol utilized to receive input	Refers to 'Required Interface information model'	Required Interfaces → Interface selection menu (Figure 3)
Expected Output	The network protocol utilized to provide output	Refers to 'Exposed Interface information model'	Exposed Interfaces → Interface creation menu (Figure 4)
Configuration Options	If any	N/A	N/A
Deployment Notes	Specific deployment notes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • E.g., descriptive scenarios for OBU or EDGE service deployment, if both are available • Exposed interfaces notes, such as network data format utilized for input/output (e.g., encoding utilized) 	N/A	N/A
Development Status	Cycle A development status	N/A	N/A

Screen captures from the referred platform GUI are provided below. Figure 1 shows the general tab for component creation. Users can access this interface to define and configure the various components within the 5G-IANA platform. Figure 2 illustrates the component creation interface in the 5G-IANA GUI that specifically focuses on the distribution parameters. Here, users can specify various parameters related to the dockerization and whether the component created will be visible to the public. The component creation interface shown in Figure 3 highlights the section for defining required interfaces for the component to be created. Users can specify the interfaces necessary for the component to receive input. Figure 4 demonstrates the tab where users can define the exposed interfaces, through which the component provides output or exposes certain functionalities. Figure 5 shows the interface for specifying the minimum execution requirements of a component during the creation process. This section allows users to define the essential resources and specifications needed for the proper execution of the component. Figure 6 and Figure 7 showcase the selection of domains

for deployment. Here the users can choose the domains where the component will be deployed. The nApp composition feature, shown in Figure 8 enables users to assemble and combine multiple components into a cohesive network application (nApp). Through the GUI, users can visually define and configure the composition of various components, specifying their interconnections and interactions. This capability allows for the creation of complex and customized network applications within the 5G-IANA platform, empowering users to develop advanced and tailored solutions for their specific use cases.

The screenshot shows the 'Components | Create' interface with the 'General' tab selected. The 'General' section contains the following fields:

- Name ***: A text input field with the placeholder 'Type your preferred name'.
- Architecture ***: A dropdown menu with the option '- Select -'.
- Elasticity Controller ***: A dropdown menu with the option '- Select -'.

Below the form, there is a checkbox labeled '(Public) If this option is checked, anyone could see this component'. At the bottom left, there is a green 'Save' button.

Figure 1: 5G-IANA GUI - Component Creation/General

The screenshot shows the 'Components | Create' interface with the 'Distribution Parameters' tab selected. The 'Distribution Parameters' section contains the following fields:

- Docker Image ***: A text input field with the placeholder 'Type the docker image'.
- Docker Credentials**: A sub-section containing:
 - Use private Docker registry (Username, Password fields)
 - Docker Username**: A text input field with the placeholder 'Type your username'.
 - Docker Password**: A text input field with the placeholder 'Type your password'.
 - Use custom docker registry
 - Custom Docker Registry**: A text input field with the placeholder 'Type the docker registry'.
 - Test Connection**: A button.

Below the form, there is a checkbox labeled '(Public) If this option is checked, anyone could see this component'. At the bottom left, there is a green 'Save' button.

Figure 2: 5G-IANA GUI - Component Creation/Distribution Parameters

Figure 3: 5G-IANA GUI - Component Creation/Required Interfaces

Figure 4: 5G-IANA GUI Component Creation/Exposed Interfaces

Figure 5: 5G-IANA GUI - Component Creation/Minimum Execution Requirements

Figure 6: 5G IANA GUI Component Creation/General Domain Selection Deployment 1/2

Figure 7: 5G IANA GUI Component Creation/General Domain Selection Deployment 2/2

Figure 8: 5G IANA GUI Component Creation nApp Composition

2.2. UC1 development status

2.2.1. Overview

UC 1 (UC1-RMD) aims to demonstrate and validate the experimentation platform developed in 5G-IANA by integrating advanced remote driving functionalities (VR, object detection and warning services) for a vehicle connected through 5G.

The 5G enabled vehicle to be used in this UC is an automated guided vehicle (AGV). This vehicle is equipped with an OBU that allows the capture of data from on-board sensors (NF#1) and the encoding of video streams (AF#1) from a set of cameras installed in the vehicle. All this data (constant feed) is transmitted through 5G (NF#3) to the Edge of the network to be processed and generate the warning corresponding to the circulation environment. The video streams are decoded at the edge (AF#1), where an AI/ML algorithm (AF#3) processes the data and provides information (added on top of the video as well) about the different objects located while driving on the road, such as pedestrians, cars, or traffic signals. Also at the edge, an additional warning feature is included using the data of the vehicle sensors, which permit to measure the distance to obstacles, to provide the driver additional information and/or stopping when a potential accident is about to happen (AF#2, AF#4). The end user will be able to see the additional

data about the AGV environment in the interface and control the connected vehicle through a steering wheel (AF#5) that sends the movements to the server to be processed by the actuator (NF#2), in charge of getting the order to the vehicle through 5G network (NF#3, AF#6).

The described service has been split into six AFs and three NFs, which are described in detail in 2.2.2. Figure 9 depicts the respective service chain.

Figure 9: UC1 Service Chain

2.2.2. AF/NF Development status

In the 5G-IANA project two main development periods have been defined, named Cycle A (M13 to M24) and Cycle B (M24 to M36). In the first period UC owners developed the initial parts of their nApps while the 5G IANA platform was developed. In the second development period the final version of both the platform and the nApps are expected. Currently, the development and integration in the 5G-IANA platform of all NFs and AFs has been done according to this timeline.

UC1 was selected as the first of the use cases to be integrated and tested with the 5G IANA platform. To achieve this, a series of steps was followed, including the access to the edge server in Nokia premises, OBU preparation and Kubernetes worker inclusion into the cluster, manual deployment of docker files with its corresponding demo in Ulm, and final onboarding process of all atomic components into the platform. These steps led

to a successful execution of a live-demo that took place in June 2023, which served as validation for cycle A. More details will be provided in WP5.

Figure 10: UC1 setup, with AFs and NFs deployed by the 5G-IANA platform (left) and vehicle with OBU and 5G modem (right) in Nokia premises, Ulm

The following tables describe the different AFs and NFs of UC1.

Table 2: AF#1 Video Encoding/Decoding

Specification Item	Description – AF#1
Name	Video Encoding/ Decoding
Version	1.0
Description	This AF encodes the video to be transmitted through the 5G network. Also responsible for decoding and playing the received video on a web application.
Deployment	Edge server + OBU (Current version only at the edge server)
Required Resources	CPU cores: 2 Memory: 4GB RAM Storage: 2GB
Exposed ports	8554, 8556, 8650, 8188
Expected Input	RTSP/H.264
Expected Output	RTSP/H.264
Configuration Options	Ports used by cameras located in vehicle
Deployment Notes	None

Development Status	Cycle A - Completed
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Table 3: AF#2 Sensor's Data Analysis

Specification Item	Description - AF#2
Name	Sensor's Data Analysis
Version	1.0
Description	Collects from sensors data related to distance and angle to near obstacles.
Deployment	Edge server
Required Resources	CPU cores: 2 Memory: 4GB RAM Storage: 2GB
Exposed ports	8765, 5678
Expected Input	NF#3, AF#4: websocket NF#1: ROS
Expected Output	NF#3, AF#4: websocket NF#1: ROS
Configuration Options	Edge and vehicle IP addresses
Deployment Notes	None
Development Status	Cycle A - Completed

Table 4: AF#3 Object Detection with Deep Learning

Specification Item	Description - AF#3
Name	Object Detection with Deep Learning
Version	1.0
Description	The video captured is processed on the edge to detect pedestrians, cars, and/or road elements such as traffic signals.
Deployment	Edge server
Required Resources	CPU cores: 4 Memory: 4GB RAM Storage: 32 GB

Exposed ports	8554, 8650, 8000
Expected Input	AF#1: RTSP/H.264 AF#4: RTSP/H.264
Expected Output	AF#1: RTSP/H.264 AF#4: RTSP/H.264
Configuration Options	Edge and Vehicle IP addresses
Deployment Notes	None
Development Status	Cycle A – Completed Cycle B – Development pending

Table 5: AF#4 Vehicle Condition Warning Service

Specification Item	Description – AF#4
Name	Vehicle Condition Warning Service
Version	1.0
Description	Representation of warning signals and alerts in the user interface.
Deployment	Edge server
Required Resources	CPU cores: 1 Memory: 2GB RAM Storage: 1GB
Exposed ports	80
Expected Input	AF#2: websocket AF#3: RTSP/H.264
Expected Output	AF#2: websocket AF#3: RTSP/H.264
Configuration Options	Edge IP address
Deployment Notes	None
Development Status	Cycle A – Completed Cycle B – Development pending

Table 6: AF#5 Remote Driving Central Control

Specification Item	Description – AF#5
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Name	Remote Driving Central Control
Version	1.0
Description	This AF is the responsible of collecting the information from the driver. Uses a steering wheel and sends it to the server to be processed by the actuator.
Deployment	HMI
Required Resources	CPU cores: 1 Memory: 2GB RAM Storage: 1GB
Exposed ports	80
Expected Input	NF#2: websocket
Expected Output	NF#2: websocket
Configuration Options	Edge IP address
Deployment Notes	None
Development Status	Cycle A – Completed Cycle B – Development pending

Table 7: AF#6 Remote Driving Module

Specification Item	Description – AF#6
Name	Remote Driving Module
Version	1.0
Description	This AF receives the orders from the actuator and moves the vehicle accordingly.
Deployment	OBU
Required Resources	CPU cores: 1 Memory: 2GB RAM Storage: 1GB
Exposed ports	9090
Expected Input	NF#2: websocket
Expected Output	NF#2: websocket
Configuration Options	n/a

Deployment Notes	None
Development Status	Cycle A – Completed

Table 8: NF#1 Sensor’s Data Capturing

Specification Item	Description – NF#1
Name	Sensor’s Data Capturing
Version	1.0
Description	Processes the information from the vehicle sensors and takes decisions regarding movement.
Deployment	OBU
Required Resources	CPU cores: 4 Memory: 4GB RAM Storage: 32 GB
Exposed ports	9090
Expected Input	NF#3, NF#2, AF#2: ROS
Expected Output	NF#3, NF#2, AF#2: ROS
Configuration Options	n/a
Deployment Notes	None
Development Status	Cycle A – Completed

Table 9: NF#2 Actuator Interface

Specification Item	Description – NF#2
Name	Actuator Interface
Version	1.0
Description	Receives the commands from the user and generates the control order in a language understood by the vehicle.
Deployment	Edge server
Required Resources	CPU cores: 2 Memory: 4GB RAM Storage: 2 GB

Exposed ports	8765, 5678
Expected Input	AF#5: websocket AF#6: ROS
Expected Output	AF#5: websocket AF#6: ROS
Configuration Options	Edge and vehicle IP address
Deployment Notes	None
Development Status	Cycle A – Completed

Table 10: NF#3 Long-Distance Data Communication

Specification Item	Description – NF#3
Name	Long-Distance Data Communication
Version	1.0
Description	This NF is in charge to transmit and to receive data for other NFs for long-distance 5G communication channel to specific edge/cloud services.
Deployment	Edge server + OBU
Required Resources	n/a
Exposed ports	None
Expected Input	AF#1: RTSP/H.264 AF#2, websocket AF#6, NF#1: ROS
Expected Output	AF#1: RTSP/H.264 AF#2, websocket AF#6, NF#1: ROS
Configuration Options	n/a
Deployment Notes	n/a
Development Status	Cycle A – Not needed

2.2.3. Identified Base nApps

The AFs and NFs described previously have been grouped in four different nApps. These groups have been selected, so the nApp can provide a particular service that can be also

reused in other UCs and scenarios (e.g. by third-parties). There are three nApps per service, i.e., real-time stream delivery, object detection and data delivery, as well as AGV control. The fourth nApp includes all functions and implements the UC itself, as defined above.

Table 11: Base nApps identified in UC1

UC1 Base nApps	ID	Name	Application/Network Functions in nApp	Brief Description
	N-UC1-1	Real Time Stream Delivery	AF#1, NF#3	The NFs and AFs in this nApp handle video encoding/decoding and streaming. AF#1 can be easily modified to use different protocols (RTP, RTSP) and codecs (H264, VP8, VP9).
	N-UC1-2	Object Detection Stream and Data Delivery	AF#1, NF#3, AF#3, AF#4	The NFs and AFs in this nApp handle video encoding/decoding and streaming. Also applies an AI algorithm to detect objects in the video streaming. AF#1 can be easily modified to use different protocols (RTP, RTSP) and codecs (H264, VP8, VP9). AF#3 can be replaced or modified with other AI algorithms.
	N-UC1-3	AGV Data Processing, Communication and Control	AF#6, NF#1, NF#3, AF#2, NF#2	The NFs and AFs in this nApp manage the communication with the vehicle and the processing of data from its sensors, making movement decisions. AF#2 can be modified to include data of new sensors in the vehicle and process their information.
	N-UC1-4	Remote Driving – UC1	All AF/NF	This nApp is made up of the entire chain of AFs/NFs for remote driving of a vehicle. It provides a user interface that facilitates vehicle control, offering a warning system and detection of nearby objects and traffic signs to help driving task. AF#5 can be easily modified to suit the needs and requirements of the user.

2.3. UC2 development status

2.3.1. Overview

UC2, Maneuver Coordination for Autonomous Driving (MCAD), aims at demonstrating the potential of the 5G-IANA platform towards exploiting connected vehicle technology

to achieve safer and more efficient traffic flows. In this UC, two similar scenarios will be presented. In the first one, a SAE level 3 autonomous vehicle will approach an intersection, so will a non-autonomous one at the same time. Both vehicles will be equipped with an OBU able to connect to an Edge server (which manages the list of connected actors with AF#3) by means of the 5G-IANA platform (specifically, NF#2 and NF#3) and exchange messages regarding different vehicle parameters (such as location, speed, among others). The proposed nApps will coordinate traversal of the intersection for all the vehicles involved (thanks to AF#2), sending a suggested path to both of them, which will follow the instructions thanks to the adaptation of the incoming messages by means of AF#1 and NF#1.

The second scenario is similar to the first one, but will allow further demonstration of the system's capabilities by proposing a considerably more critical situation, in which the junction is affected by heavy traffic. In this case, the number of physical vehicles will be the same, but a higher quantity of vehicles will be virtually present by means of a digital twin of the intersection in the CARLA simulator. These virtual vehicles will be equipped with vOBUs, which are equal to their physical counterparts in terms of what the nApp will interface with. Therefore, they will be treated just as real vehicles, while allowing for more difficult situations to be tested without putting anyone at risk and with marginal increases in cost.

The nApp at the core of UC2 will be the MCAD, which will utilize the received information from all vehicles in order to solve the intersection problem in the best possible way in terms of safety and efficiency, and to then send the instructions to all involved vehicles by means of Maneuver Coordination Messages.

Figure 11 depicts the respective service chain.

Figure 11: UC2 Service Chain

2.3.2. AF/NF Development Status

Table 12: AF#1 Vehicle interface

Specification Item	Description – AF#1
Name	Vehicle interface
Version	1.0
Description	This AF receives commands from the maneuver planning user and semantically adapts it for the vehicle.
Deployment	OBU
Required Resources	n/a
Exposed ports	n/a
Expected Input	NF#1, NF#2
Expected Output	NF#1, NF#2
Configuration Options	n/a

Deployment Notes	none
Development Status	Cycle A – Early Development

Table 13: AF#2 Maneuver planning

Specification Item	Description – AF#2
Name	Maneuver planning
Version	1.0
Description	This AF receives information from subscription service for enrolling and from OBUs to compute the available maneuvers for the vehicles to act.
Deployment	EDGE SERVER
Required Resources	n/a
Exposed ports	n/a
Expected Input	NF#2
Expected Output	NF#2
Configuration Options	n/a
Deployment Notes	None
Development Status	Cycle A - Early development

Table 14: AF#3 Subscription Service

Specification Item	Description – AF#3
Name	Subscription Service
Version	1.0
Description	The service enables the enrolling of vehicles to the MCAD nApp to let them participate to the maneuver coordination.
Deployment	Cloud
Required Resources	n/a
Exposed ports	n/a
Expected Input	AF#2
Expected Output	AF#2

Configuration Options	n/a
Deployment Notes	None
Development Status	Cycle B - Programmed

Table 15: NF#1 Vehicle abstraction

Specification Item	Description – NF#1
Name	Vehicle abstraction
Version	1.0
Description	This NF guarantees protocol compatibility between vehicle and the Vehicle Interface.
Deployment	OBU
Required Resources	n/a
Exposed ports	n/a
Expected Input	NF#1, NF#2
Expected Output	NF#1, NF#2
Configuration Options	n/a
Deployment Notes	None
Development Status	Cycle A

Table 16: NF#2 C-ITS messages long-distance communication

Specification Item	Description – NF#2
Name	C-ITS messages long-distance communication
Version	1.0
Description	This NF is in charge to transmit and receive data for other NFs for long-distance 5G communication channel to specific edge/cloud services.
Deployment	EDGE SERVER+OBU
Required Resources	n/a
Exposed ports	n/a
Expected Input	NF#3, AF#1

Expected Output	NF#3, AF#1
Configuration Options	n/a
Deployment Notes	None
Development Status	Cycle A

Table 17: NF#3-ETSI maneuver coordination service

Specification Item	Description - NF#3
Name	ETSI maneuver coordination service
Version	1.0
Description	This NF implements the functionalities of the ETSI Maneuver Coordination Service.
Deployment	EDGE SERVER+OBU
Required Resources	n/a
Exposed ports	n/a
Expected Input	NF#2, NF#3 (counterpart instance)
Expected Output	NF#2, NF#3 (counterpart instance)
Configuration Options	n/a
Deployment Notes	None
Development Status	Cycle A

2.3.3. Identified Base nApps

Table 18: Base nApps identified in UC2

UC2 Base nApps	ID	Name	Application/Network Functions in nApp	Brief Description
	N-UC2-1	MCAD rover node	AF#1, NF#1, NF#2, NF#3	Duplex communication between MCAD Edge node and a vehicle. This nApp manages vehicular functions so as to translate received maneuver coordination messages to vehicular commands and vice-versa, by transmitting vehicle pose and status.

	N-UC2-2	MCAD edge node	NF#2, NF#3, AF#2	Uses ETSI maneuver coordination messages to manage an intersection by means of the generation of trajectories for the vehicles approaching it.
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The following are more detailed descriptions of the nApps for UC2:

MCAD rover node is a nApp designed to reside in an OBU attached to a vehicle. From one side, it will translate data coming from the vehicle’s internal networks (such as CAN) into ETSI Maneuver Coordination Service [1], so vehicular information can be used by the MCAD edge node. On the other hand, incoming ETSI messages will be translated to the protocols of the vehicle, so the appropriate commands can be issued, whether it be actual vehicle inputs like throttle or steering in the case of an AV or HMI messages for a human-driven vehicle.

MCAD edge node is the nApp designed to manage the safe traversal of an intersection for all the vehicles which approach it. As such, it will receive information from all the OBUs registered to its accompanying subscription service. This information will regard vehicular poses, speeds and processed environment data, which is used by this nApp to determine the best trajectories and speeds the vehicles will have to follow. Once they are determined, this nApp sends the appropriate ETSI maneuver coordination messages to each involved vehicle.

2.4. UC3 development status

2.4.1. Overview

UC3 will demonstrate a virtual bus tour. During the tour, users will be joining a VR space (AF#6) of a bus and be represented there via avatars. The VR users will be able to choose from a collection of avatars, one per role per biological gender. Through their avatar the users will be able to communicate via voice, and gesture to each other, while the 360 footage is being displayed around them. A vehicle will drive through the predefined tour route, providing the users with a 360° video of the tour surroundings streamed by a high-resolution camera capable of providing 2160p 30fps livestream footage. To comply with data protection principles of the countries where this UC will be demonstrated, namely in NOKIA testbed, Ulm Germany and Telecom Slovenia testbed, in Slovenia, a privacy masking module (AF#1) is utilized, to blur the identified private sensitive data. The video will be encoded in streams of different qualities (AF#2) and adaptive bitrate streaming will be utilized to adapt the video quality based on the available network bandwidth, which will be actively monitored by the corresponding module (NF#2). Finally, a load

balancer provided by NXW which will act as a reverse proxy will be available to provide an exposed endpoint to the VR clients (AF#4, NXW). For the duration of the trip, a tour guide will provide information concerning the attractions seen while additional details will be available via GPS-driven landmark indicators. The positional data provided will orient through the position and time service NF provided by LINKS (NF#8, see Table 59).

In order to reduce the utilized radio resources for the video transmission, an AI enabled mechanism that predicts the point-of-view of the users (NF#3, NF#5, AF#3, AF#6), will be functioning on the background. Based on this mechanism, the video stream is catered to reduce the network and computational resources utilized by the nApp. Finally, a service will be available to save logs related to the UC (NF#7, AF#5).

Figure 12 depicts the respective service chain.

Figure 12: UC3 Service Chain

2.4.2. AF/NF Development Status

Table 19: AF#1 Privacy Masking Module

Specification Item	Description – AF#1
Name	Privacy Masking Module
Version	1.0
Description	This AF applies privacy masking to the 360° video stream used in UC3, meaning that footage of pedestrians passing

	by, car plates etc. is blurred for anonymization. Different AI models is used for plate/face recognition.
Deployment	OBU
Required Resources	GPU Memory: >8GB RAM CPU: > 2 vCores Storage: < 2GB
Exposed ports	1935
Expected Input	Camera video stream via PULL strategy (RTMP/RTSP)
Expected Output	AF#3: RTMP
Configuration Options	The video stream server specifics for the masking module to be able to pull the stream are provided as configuration 1) camera's server URL 2)resolution in the form of [p2160, p1440, p1080, p720,] 3)stream FPS.
Deployment Notes	None
Development Status	Cycle A – On track

Table 20: AF#2 Live stream Encoder

Specification Item	Description – AF#2
Name	Live stream Encoder
Version	1.0
Description	This AF handles the video encoding i.e., compressions and re-encoding tasks. The anonymized stream is split into tiles and encoded into MPEG-DASH and HLS stream i.e., use of chunks at different qualities. It will receive information from #NF2 to decide if compression is needed.
Deployment	OBU
Required Resources	RAM: >16GBb CPU: > 4 vCores Storage: < 1GB
Exposed ports	1936, 8080

Expected Input	AF#3 – RTMP
Expected Output	NF#1 – MPEG-DASH & HLS
Configuration Options	Nginx configuration file can be provided. Ports & input may alter depending on the configuration
Deployment Notes	None
Development Status	Cycle A – On track

Table 21: AF#3 360 Video Slicer

Specification Item	Description – AF#3
Name	360 Video Slicer
Version	1.0
Description	This AF masks the 360° video so that the parts where the users focus have high resolution while the remaining parts have low resolution.
Deployment	OBU
Required Resources	N/A
Exposed ports	1937, 8090
Expected Input	AF#1 - RTMP
Expected Output	AF#2 - RTMP
Configuration Options	n/a
Deployment Notes	n/a
Development Status	Cycle B - Not started

Table 22: AF#4 Load Balancer (NXW)

Specification Item	Description – AF#4
Name	Load Balancer (NXW)
Version	1.0
Description	The Load Balancer is based on HAProxy [2] and BIND9 [3].
Deployment	EDGE SERVER
Required Resources	n/a

Exposed ports	n/a
Expected Input	RTMP
Expected Output	RTMP
Configuration Options	HAProxy configuration
Deployment Notes	n/a
Development Status	Cycle A – Completed

Table 23: AF#5 UC-Specific Log Reporting Service

Specification Item	Description – AF#5
Name	UC-Specific Log Reporting Service
Version	1.0
Description	A Database (MongoDB) is utilized to save logs related to the UC.
Deployment	Core
Required Resources	Ram < 2GB CPU < 1vCore storage > 10GB
Exposed ports	1883
Expected Input	NF#7 - MQTT
Expected Output	None
Configuration Options	n/a
Deployment Notes	None
Development Status	Cycle A – Completed

Table 24: AF#6 Field of View Predictor

Specification Item	Description – AF#6
Name	Field of View Predictor
Version	1.0
Description	This AF utilizes Deep Learning AI techniques to predict the future Points-of-View for the VR users.

Deployment	EDGE SERVER
Required Resources	RAM > 8GB CPU > 4cores Storage > 10GB
Exposed ports	8080
Expected Input	NF#3 - MQTT
Expected Output	NF#3 - MQTT, HTTP
Configuration Options	n/a
Deployment Notes	None
Development Status	Cycle B – Development has begun

Table 25: NF#1 360 video stream Endpoint

Specification Item	Description – NF#1
Name	360 video stream Endpoint
Version	1.0
Description	This NF facilitates sending the 360° Video Stream from the Far Edge to Edge Cloud by employing caching & traffic shaping based on the network resources available.
Deployment	OBU
Required Resources	RAM: < 1GB CPU: < 2vCores Storage: < 1GB
Exposed ports	3128, 9090
Expected Input	NF#2 - HTTP
Expected Output	NF#4 - HTTP
Configuration Options	Traffic shape strategy
Deployment Notes	None
Development Status	Cycle B – Development has started

Table 26: NF#2 Active Network Monitoring Module

Specification Item	Description – NF#2
Name	Active Network Monitoring Module
Version	1.0
Description	This NF provides a mechanism that will estimate the available network bandwidth utilizing active probing. This estimation will be used as input to the Video Encoder AF.
Deployment	EDGE SERVER
Required Resources	RAM: < 1GB CPU: < 2vCores Storage: < 1GB
Exposed ports	80, 8080
Expected Input	NF#2: TCP
Expected Output	AF#2: HTTP, NF#2: TCP
Configuration Options	n/a
Deployment Notes	None
Development Status	Cycle B – Development has started

Table 27: NF#3 Foveated Rendering Sink

Specification Item	Description – NF#3
Name	Foveated Rendering Sink
Version	1.0
Description	This NF receives foveatic data (i.e., “fixation points”) from the Field of View (FOV) Predictor AF and provides it to the Video Slicer AF. Foveating imaging is a technique where image resolution, or amount of detail, varies across the image according to one or more “fixation points”.
Deployment	EDGE SERVER
Required Resources	RAM: <1GB CPU < 2vCores Storage <= 1GB
Exposed ports	1883

Expected Input	AF3: MQTT
Expected Output	MQTT
Configuration Options	n/a
Deployment Notes	None
Development Status	Cycle B – not started

Table 28: NF#4 Video Stream Cache

Specification Item	Description – NF#4
Name	Video Stream Cache
Version	1.0
Description	This NF handles the 360° Video Stream and acts as a buffering mechanism that will be employed to maintain video fidelity to the end users, even in no network service availability scenarios.
Deployment	EDGE SERVER
Required Resources	RAM > 2GB CPU > 2vCores Storage > 10GB
Exposed ports	8128, 9090
Expected Input	NF#1 - HTTP
Expected Output	AF#4 - HTTP
Configuration Options	n/a
Deployment Notes	None
Development Status	Cycle B – development has started

Table 29: NF#5 Foveated Rendering Data Broker

Specification Item	Description – NF#5
Name	Foveated Rendering Data Broker
Version	1.0

Description	This NF is a data broker that receives foveatic data (i.e., point of view) from the VR users and acts as a broker for related modules located in the Far Edge.
Deployment	EDGE SERVER
Required Resources	RAM: <1GB CPU < 2vCore Storage <= 1GB
Exposed ports	1883
Expected Input	NF#3: MQTT AF#4: MQTT
Expected Output	NF#3: MQTT AF#4: MQTT
Configuration Options	RabbitMQ configuration
Deployment Notes	None
Development Status	Cycle B – development has started

Table 30: NF#6 VR Server Module

Specification Item	Description – NF#6
Name	VR Server Module
Version	1.0
Description	An authoritative Unity server that is the backbone the VR application facilitating the Virtual Bus Tour presented in UC3.
Deployment	EDGE SERVER
Required Resources	CPU > 2vCores, RAM > 4GB, Storage > 2GB
Exposed ports	7777, 8099
Expected Input	NF#8: MQTT HTTP - Management layer VRClients : Reliable - UDP
Expected Output	VRClients : Reliable - UDP
Configuration Options	Stream URL
Deployment Notes	None
Development Status	Cycle B – development on track

Table 31: NF#7 Log Reporting Service Data Broker

Specification Item	Description – NF#7
Name	Log Reporting Service Data Broker
Version	1.0
Description	NF that exposes UC related data e.g., location-based data stored in AF#5. Used either for UC specific functionalities and for debugging/monitoring purposes.
Deployment	EDGE SERVER
Required Resources	RAM: < 1GB CPU: < 2vCores Storage: > 1GB
Exposed ports	1883
Expected Input	#AF5: MQTT
Expected Output	#AF5: MQTT
Configuration Options	n/a
Deployment Notes	None
Development Status	Cycle A – On track

2.4.3. Identified Base nApps

The AFs and NFs described in section 2.4.2 have been grouped in four different nApps. The purpose of those nApps is to provide a reusable network service which could accommodate multiple scenarios and be a stepping stone for third-party experimenters interested in the infotainment and automotive verticals.

Table 32: Base nApps identified in UC3

	ID	Name	Application/Network Functions in nApp	Brief Description
UC3 Base nApps	N-UC3-1	AI Enhanced Video Stream Delivery	AF#1, AF#2, AF#3, AF#4, NF#1, NF#4	The NFs and AFs in this nApp provide a service capable of receiving a 360° livestream and providing a ABR stream endpoint resilient to network instability, whose bandwidth is significantly limited via its FOV prediction AI mechanism.

N-UC3-2	Video enabled VR Client	NF#1, NF#4, NF#6	The NFs in this nApp provide a VR service that can utilize a 360° live video as a background.
N-UC3-3	Active Network Monitoring Module	NF#2 (two instances)	NF#2 monitors the network for bandwidth availability and can be utilized as a service for any other nApp that would benefit from such a functionality.
N-UC3-4	Virtual Bus Tour - UC3	All AF/NF	This nApp is made up of the entire chain of AFs/NFs that enable the Virtual Bus tour showcased in UC3.

2.5. UC4 development status

2.5.1. Overview

UC4 is considered a nApp that will use a combination of edge computing and AR technology to offload the computing power needed to display high-quality 3D objects, rendered by an AR engine, and stream them down to AR-enabled devices. The 3D objects streaming will be provided to the 3D navigation environment of Live View by using ARCore Geospatial API and Edge Server. It is challenging for AR applications to support marker-based (and not marker-less) AR streaming content with the help of Edge elements to minimize the battery consumption of the mobile device. Marker-less AR is used to denote an AR application that does not need prior knowledge of a user's environment. Marker-based AR apps use markers (i.e., target images) to indicate things in a given space. The application could be both for road users using an OBU and mobile users using a mobile phone while driving for future AR enabled navigation services over 5G. Such AR streaming application will consider different settings of the UE (OBU or mobile phone) such as location, context, speed, and throughput. A significant aspect of the Intelligent nApp is that it will exploit the Edge Server existence and capabilities, bringing the services of the application closer to the user. This will satisfy the need for QoS, delivering a high-quality AR content including virtual 3D objects and text in low latency as well as maximizing the availability and reliability of the functions. The Intelligent nApp will also take into consideration the coverage of the offered network in Ulm combined with the user's speed so it will adjust to the system requirements.

Figure 13 depicts the respective service chain.

Figure 13: UC4 Service Chain

2.5.2. AF/NF Development Status

Table 33: AF#1 Virtualized Cache

Specification Item	Description – AF#1
NF Name	Virtualized Cache
NF Version	1.0
Description	Caching valuable data for faster service, such as mobile phone data, 3D Objects and text.
Deployment	EDGE SERVER
Required Resources	CPU: > 2vCores Memory: > 1GB RAM Storage: > 1GB
Exposed ports	4442
Expected Input	AF#3: AR Media Access function (TCP)
Expected Output	AF#3: AR Media Access function (TCP)
Configuration Options	n/a

Deployment Notes	None
Development Status	Cycle A

Table 34: AF#2 AR content repository

Specification Item	Description - AF#2
NF Name	AR content repository
NF Version	1.0
Description	Storage for AR content such as 3D objects and text.
Deployment	EDGE SERVER
Required Resources	CPU: > 2vCores Memory: > 1GB RAM Storage: > 1GB
Exposed ports	4443
Expected Input	AF#3: AR Media Access Function (TCP)
Expected Output	AF#3: AR Media Access Function (TCP)
Configuration Options	n/a
Deployment Notes	None
Development Status	Cycle A

Table 35: AF#3 AR media access function

Specification Item	Description - AF#3
NF Name	AR media access function
NF Version	1.0
Description	This NF is in charge to give access to the mobile device to the AR content through an access media functionality that relies on a specific streaming protocol.
Deployment	EDGE SERVER
Required Resources	CPU: > 2vCores Memory: > 1GB RAM Storage: < 2GB

Exposed ports	4444
Expected Input	AF#1: Virtualized Cache (TCP) AF#2: AR content repository (TCP)
Expected Output	AF#1: Virtualized Cache (TCP) AF#2: AR content repository (TCP)
Configuration Options	n/a
Deployment Notes	None
Development Status	Cycle A

Table 36: AF#4 Load balancer

Specification Item	Description – AF#4
NF Name	Load balancer
NF Version	1.0
Description	Load balancing between cloud and edge.
Deployment	CLOUD
Required Resources	CPU: > 2vCores Memory: > 1GB RAM Storage: > 1GB
Exposed ports	4465
Expected Input	NF#2: Network Monitoring (TCP)
Expected Output	NF#2: Network Monitoring (TCP)
Configuration Options	n/a
Deployment Notes	None
Development Status	Cycle A

Table 37: NF#1 Long-Distance Data Communication

Specification Item	Description – NF#1
NF Name	Long-Distance Data Communication
NF Version	1.0

Description	This NF is in charge to transmit and to receive data for other NFs for long-distance 5G communication channel to specific edge/cloud services.
Deployment	EDGE SERVER + MOBILE PHONE
Required Resources	n/a
Exposed ports	n/a
Expected Input	AF#3: AR Media Access Function
Expected Output	AF#3: AR Media Access Function
Configuration Options	n/a
Deployment Notes	None
Development Status	Cycle A

Table 38: NF#2 Network monitoring

Specification Item	Description – NF#2
NF Name	Network monitoring
NF Version	1.0
Description	Monitors the network behaviour, by tracking metrics such as network latency, bandwidth, network traffic for high-quality user experience.
Deployment	EDGE SERVER + MOBILE PHONE
Required Resources	CPU: > 2vCores Memory: > 1GB RAM Storage: > 1GB
Exposed ports	4466
Expected Input	AF#4: Load Balancer (TCP)
Expected Output	AF#4: Load Balancer (TCP)
Configuration Options	n/a
Deployment Notes	None
Development Status	Cycle A

2.5.3. Identified Base nApps

The AFs and NFs described in Section 2.5.2 have been grouped in two different nApps. These nApps have been identified and can provide services to both AR content and technology providers (i.e. N-UC4-1 and N-UC4-2) respectively. The two nApps are the AR app running on the mobile phone and the AR streaming application that is running on the server side.

Table 39: Base nApps identified in UC4.

	ID	Name	Application/Network Functions in nApp	Brief Description
UC4 Base nApps	N-UC4-1	AR App	AF#1, NF#2	The NF#2 and AF#1 in this nApp of UC4 handle AR objects rendering on the mobile phone.
	N-UC4-2	AR streaming application	AF#1, AF#2, AF#3, AF#4, NF#1, NF#2	The NF#2 and AF#1 with AF#2 plus AF#3 in this nApp of UC4 handle the AR objects streaming through specific AR streaming protocols and buffering. AF#4 with NF#1 are related to the network monitoring and connection.

2.6. UC5 development status

2.6.1. Overview

UC5 will develop a novel driving safety feature, which will detect aggressive and distracted driving (AF#3) and will transmit warning notifications on road risk-level increase to other vehicles (AF#2, NF#1, NF#2, NF#3). We will distinguish between two kinds of hazardous events: aggressive driving (harsh braking, harsh acceleration, speeding, crashes) and distracted driving (mobile use).

UC5 will employ two sources of data: a) the driver's mobile phone, which will provide gyroscope, compass and accelerometer data, and b) an OBU installed in the vehicle, which will provide GPS and position data (AF#1). These two sources of data will be combined to detect hazardous events (AF#3). In addition, an ML model to be trained with high-frequency vehicle data from the OBU to make notifications more relevant to the user will be developed (AF#4). This model will predict the vehicle's trajectory in order for the notifications to be more accurate. To complement the data pool, O7 will develop an ML model that will operate on the edge, based on aggregated data (PoC for the project needs, to be based on current O7 data or mock data) and enriched with real-time

data for the collection of aggregate data along road segments, assigning an aggregate risk level (AF#5).

The combination of real-time data (AF#1, AF#3, AF#4) and the aggregate data (AF#5) will allow UC5 users to be notified in advance on the increase of risks levels of the road they are driving on (AF#2, NF#1, NF#2, NF#3). This will increase driver awareness and decrease their reaction time, while also enhancing driver visibility in low visibility case (e.g., fog, low- lighting conditions, junctions). The feature will distribute the information on a many-to-many integrated approach (AF#2, NF#1, NF#2, NF#3), detecting hazardous events from many vehicles and notifying many vehicles in real time.

Five AFs and three NFs will be used in UC5, Four novel AFs will be developed by O7 (AF#2, AF#3, AF#4, and AF#5) while the remaining functions are available and will be modified. All functions will be completed during Cycle A of the project development, while fine tunings and improvements will take place during Cycle B, when deviations will be identified during testing.

Figure 14: UC5 Service Chain

Figure 14 depicts the respective service chain.

2.6.2. AF/NF Development Status

Table 40: AF#2 Hazardous event receiver and display

Specification Item	Description – AF#2
Name	Hazardous event receiver and display
Version	1.0

Description	Receives and displays a warning notification on hazardous events on the road.
Deployment	OBU
Required Resources	CPU: < 1 vCPU RAM: < 1GB RAM Storage: < 1GB
Exposed ports	1935
Expected Input	High risk data provided by the Hazardous Driving Behaviour Detection NF and Position and Time information provided by B-VNF08 and smartphone sensors.
Expected Output	A message displaying high risk warnings via the UC2 HMI
Configuration Options	n/a
Deployment Notes	None
Development Status	Cycle A – On track

Table 41: AF#3 Hazardous driving behaviour detection

Specification Item	Description – AF#3
Name	Hazardous driving behaviour detection
Version	1.0
Description	Detects hazardous events during driving: harsh braking, harsh acceleration, speeding, and mobile use.
Deployment	OBU
Required Resources	< 1 vCPU, < 1GB RAM, < 1GB storage
Exposed ports	1935
Expected Input	Position and time information provided by B-VNF08 (Position and Time Service) and smartphone sensors for calculating hazardous driving events.
Expected Output	High-risk events that will be transferred to the Hazardous event receiver and display NF.
Configuration Options	n/a
Deployment Notes	None

Development Status	Cycle A – On track
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Table 42: AF#4 Vehicle trajectory prediction

Specification Item	Description – AF#4
Name	Vehicle trajectory prediction
Version	1.0
Description	This NF is responsible for the interference of an ML model that predicts the car’s trajectory in order to make the notifications more accurate.
Deployment	OBU
Required Resources	CPU: < 1 vCPU RAM: < 1GB Storage: < 1GB
Exposed ports	1935
Expected Input	Position and time information is provided by B-VNF08 (Position and Time Service, Table 59) and hazardous events detected by B-VNF-53. (Hazardous driving behaviour detection)
Expected Output	Correction to the trajectory of the vehicle to B-VNF-52 (Hazardous event receiver and display) so that the notification of hazardous events is more accurate
Configuration Options	n/a
Deployment Notes	None
Development Status	Cycle A – Completed

Table 43: AF#5 Aggregated Road risk level

Specification Item	Description – AF#5
Name	Aggregated road risk level
Version	1.0
Description	ML model to operate on the edge for the assessment of the risk level of a road network, based on aggregated data (from sources such as telematics service) and enriched by real-time data
Deployment	Edge Server

Required Resources	CPU: < 1 vCPU RAM: < 1GB Storage: < 1GB
Exposed ports	3000, 8080 (REST)
Expected Input	Position and time information provided by B-VNF08 (Position and time service) and hazardous events detected by B-VNF-53 (Hazardous driving behaviour detection).
Expected Output	Road risk level information based on aggregated data
Configuration Options	n/a
Deployment Notes	None
Development Status	Cycle A – On Track

2.6.3. Identified Base nApps

The AFs and NFs described in Section 2.6.2 have been grouped in four different nApps. These nApps have been identified and can provide services to all UC stakeholders (e.g., insurance companies, fleet management companies, leasing/rental companies) based on their particular demands.

Table 44: Base nApps identified in UC5

	ID	Name	Application/Network Functions in nApp	Brief Description
UC Base nApps	N-UC5-1	Real-time Hazardous driving event detection	AF#1, AF#3, NF#1, NF#2, NF#3	The NFs and AFs in this nApp handle real-time hazardous driving behaviour detection and risk event notification. Hazardous driving behaviour detection AF interfaces the smartphone and OBU and can be easily modified to allow the addition of other AI algorithms to interact with the driving behaviour data.
	N-UC5-2	Aggregated Hazardous driving event detection	AF#1, AF#3, AF#5, NF#1, NF#4, NF#6	The NFs and AFs in this nApp handle hazardous driving behaviour detection and risk event notification based on aggregated data. Hazardous driving behaviour detection AF and Aggregated Road risk level AF interface the smartphone and OBU and can be easily modified to allow the addition of other AI

			algorithms to interact with the driving behaviour data.
N-UC5-3	Real-time vehicle trajectory prediction	AF#1, AF#4, NF#1, NF#2, NF#3	The NFs and AFs in this nApp will provide corrections to the vehicle's current trajectory in order to accurately predict its future trajectory.
N-UC5-4	Hazardous driving event notification – UC5	All AF/NF	This nApp will subscribe to events from ETSI decentralized environmental notification service NF and will identify the appropriate hazardous events to display to the driver and also warn them when they enter a high-risk road segment.

2.7. UC6 development status

2.7.1. Overview

UC6 provides an overview of the status of network components or virtual network functions and draws conclusions and predictions concerning the performance of the monitored components. It utilizes V2X communications to deliver predictions of the network quality to a central computation entity at the EDGE server. This UC aims to minimize the data collection effort by utilizing a Distributed Machine Learning (DML) approach, i.e., instead of collecting large amounts of network monitoring data to be centrally analyzed, the ML analysis/prediction model is distributed on the NFs/AFs located at the vehicle OBUs. The goal of the ML model is:

1. to learn data traffic patterns for data traffic prediction,
2. to learn network condition models to provide QoS predictions, and
3. to learn to distinguish between normal and abnormal network behaviors to detect and predict faults.

The UC implementation relies on six AFs and one NFs as specified in Table 45 - Table 50. The functions are being entirely developed during Cycle A to meet the objectives of the UC. Fine tunings and specific improvements will follow during Cycle B when deviations will be identified during testing.

AF#1 (Position and Time Service, Table 59) and AF#6 (Network Monitoring, Table 49) collect the data needed for model training and inference. The GPS coordinates of the vehicle are collected by AF#1, and AF#6 collects application layer network metrics such as Round Trip Time (RTT) and Throughput by sniffing the application packets. The data

collected by these AFs in OBU is preprocessed by AF#3 (ML Preprocessing, Table 46) to prepare it for ML training.

AF#5 (DML Aggregation Node, Table 48) after receiving the model and the training parameters from the client, forwards them to AF#4 (DML Node-Training Agent, Table 47). AF#4 collects the prepared data from AF#3 and trains the model received from AF#5. The trained models from all the OBUs are forwarded to AF#5 for aggregation to have a single global model. This global is then forwarded to AF#4 on all the OBUs for the second round of training. This process is continued until the model achieves optimum performance as mentioned in training parameters set by the client.

This optimum model is used in AF#2 (QoS Prediction, Table 45) to predict future application-level network behavior (RTT and Throughput).

Figure 15: UC6 Service Chain

The UC implementation relies on six AFs and one NFs. The functions are being entirely developed during Cycle A in order to meet the objectives of the UC. Fine tunings and specific improvements will follow during Cycle B when deviations will be identified during testing. Figure 15 depicts the respective service chain.

2.7.2. AF/NF Development Status

Table 45: AF#2-QoS prediction

Specification Item	Description - AF#2
Name	QoS prediction
Version	1.0
Description	The AF is based on the trained Distributed ML model at the far-edge node. An LSTM prediction model is trained on each far-edge node (AF#4) and aggregated in AF#5 (DML Aggregation Node) present on the Edge. This aggregated global model is then transmitted to all the far-edge nodes for further training. The optimum model obtained after multiple training cycles is used for predictions.
Deployment	EDGE SERVER+OBU
Required Resources	CPU: 1core RAM: 4GB Storage: >2GB GPU
Exposed ports	None
Expected Input	AF#5: Sockets (TCP)
Expected Output	AF#5: Sockets (TCP)
Configuration Options	None
Deployment Notes	None
Development Status	Cycle A

Table 46: AF#3 ML pre-processing

Specification Item	Description - AF#3
Name	ML pre-processing

Version	1.0
Description	This AF prepares the data collected by Network Monitoring AF for training.
Deployment	EDGE SERVER+OBU
Required Resources	CPU: 1core RAM: 4GB Storage: >2GB GPU
Exposed ports	None
Expected Input	AF#6: HTTPS AF#4: Sockets (TCP)
Expected Output	AF#6: HTTPS AF#4: Sockets (TCP)
Configuration Options	n/a
Deployment Notes	None
Development Status	Cycle A

Table 47: AF#4 ML node-training agent

Specification Item	Description - AF#4
Name	ML node-training agent
Version	1.0
Description	The AF trains the model using a locally collected data set. This model is sent to the aggregation AF. After the aggregation, the AF receives a new globally trained model for further training.
Deployment	EDGE SERVER+OBU
Required Resources	GPU : >2GB CPU : 1core RAM : 4 GB Storage: 10GB
Exposed ports	None
Expected Input	AF#5: Sockets (TCP) AF#3: Sockets (TCP)
Expected Output	AF#5: Sockets (TCP)

	AF#3: Sockets (TCP)
Configuration Options	None
Deployment Notes	None
Development Status	Cycle A

Table 48: AF#5 DML aggregation node

Specification Item	Description – AF#5
Name	DML aggregation node
Version	1.0
Description	The AF receives the locally trained DML models from all the worker nodes (far-edges) and aggregates them. After aggregation, it forwards the aggregated model to all the working nodes.
Deployment	EDGE SERVER+OBU
Required Resources	CPU: 1core, RAM:4GB
Exposed ports	n/a
Expected Input	AF#4: Sockets (TCP)
Expected Output	AF#4: Sockets (TCP)
Configuration Options	None
Deployment Notes	None
Development Status	Cycle A

Table 49: AF#6 Network monitoring

Specification Item	Description – AF#6
Name	Network monitoring
Version	1.0
Description	The NF monitors the network behaviour passively and actively from the edge. It sniffs the application packets received by the edge and calculates network-based metrics (such as data rate and latency).
Deployment	EDGE SERVER+OBU

Required Resources	GPS module
Exposed ports	None
Expected Input	AF#3: HTTPS
Expected Output	AF#3: HTTPS
Configuration Options	None
Deployment Notes	None
Development Status	Cycle A

Table 50: NF#1 Long-distance communication

Specification Item	Description – NF#1
Name	Long-distance communication
Version	1.0
Description	This NF is in charge of transmitting and receiving data for other NFs for the long-distance communication channel to specific edge/cloud services.
Deployment	EDGE SERVER+OBU
Required Resources	n/a
Exposed ports	None
Expected Input	AF#3: HTTPS
Expected Output	AF#3: HTTPS
Configuration Options	None
Deployment Notes	None
Development Status	Cycle A

2.7.3. Identified Base nApps

Based on AFs and NFs presented in Section 2.7.2, three nApps have been defined (see Table 51). These nApps are considered “standalone,” meaning each one can be independently used in other UCs and, as such available on the AOEP platform to be used by third-party developers. However, besides utilizing 5G network and cloud-continuum

infrastructure, nApps are utilizing specific IoT devices, which also needs to be considered when applying to a UC.

This UC can be integrated with other UCs, such as UC1 (Remote Driving) and UC3 (Virtual Bus Tour). The synergies between the UCs benefit both parties. For example, the remote vehicle controller of UC1 can make better remote manoeuvring decisions based on the network behaviour estimates provided by the Predictive QoS (N-UC6-1) nApp of UC6. Furthermore, the Predictive QoS nApp is being packaged such that any other UC can incorporate this nApp without much adjustment and use the network predictions for their applications.

pQoS nApp implements the functionalities of the Predictive Quality of Services which predicts the future network status the vehicles are going to experience. We train the LSTM model in federated fashion to predict the network latency (Round-trip time) and throughput quantiles.

The pQoS nApp receives network measurement data (latency and throughput) experienced by the OBU as an input to predict the future quantiles. This nApp is composed of AF#2 QoS Prediction (Table 45).

Obtain Training Data nApp makes the network measurement data available for training and inference. The nApp includes two AFs, AF#6 (Network Monitoring, Table 49), which collects the network status from the Far-Edge/OBUs and AF#3 (ML Pre-processing Node, Table 46), which prepares the data collected by AF#6.

AF#6, collects the network monitoring passively by sniffing the applications packets of the OBUs, such that no additional network traffic is generated to measure the network status (such as latency and throughput).

AF#3, handles the job of cleaning the data and preparing it (perform operations like normalizing, sorting, distributing or even transforming) for training and inference.

DML Training nApp trains the local models of each OBU with the training data collected by the N-UC6-2 (Table 51). The trained models from all the OBUs are further aggregated at the EDGE to form a single global model.

This nApp includes 2 AFs, AF#4 (ML node Training agent, Table 47) and AF#5 (ML Aggregator node, Table 48).

AF#5, is the aggregator node in federated learning architecture. It receives the model to be trained from the clients and forwards the model to all the OBUs. AF#4 deployed at each OBU, is responsible for training the model (send by AF#5) using the data it collects and forwards the trained model to the AF#5. AF#5 (Aggregator node), then aggregates

all the models it receives from various OBUs into one global model. This global model is then forwarded to OBUs for training and the cycle is repeated.

Table 51: Base nApps identified in UC6

	ID	Name	Application/Network Functions in nApp	Brief Description
UC6 Base nApps	N-UC6-1	Predictive QoS	AF#2	This nApp takes spatial and temporal data input and provides a prediction for QoS metrics such as latency and throughput. It is based on the trained distributed ML model present at the Far-Edge node. An LSTM prediction model is trained on each Far-Edge node and aggregated at the aggregator node. This aggregated global model is then transmitted to all the Far-edge nodes for training and finally inference (i.e. prediction).
	N-UC6-2	Obtain Training Data	AF#3 and AF#6	This nApp collects the network status such as round-trip time, and data rate, and processes it suitable for training.
	N-UC6-3	DML Training	AF#4 and AF#5	This nApp trains the local models of each OBU with the training data collected by the previous nApp. The trained models from all the OBUs are further aggregated at the EDGE to form a single Global model.

2.8. UC7 development status

2.8.1. Overview

UC7 will demonstrate a solution providing situational awareness for first responders intervening in the cross-border road tunnel in case of an accident or any other emergency. To achieve this, UC7 aims to develop and integrate solution specific hardware and software components such as NFs, RSU, OBUs, various sensors and camera. RSU and IoT sensors connected to it (e.g., temperature, CO and CO2 levels, camera), as well as OBUs, will provide environmental data sensed in a tunnel, including real-time video-stream. Functions deployed in RSU and OBUs will take care of collecting and initially processing collected data and will provide data transmission to the EDGE SERVER/cloud where further data processing will take place. Also, data stored in databases located at EDGE SERVER/cloud will be available for other components (incl. third-party components) to utilize them. Therefore, functions for data collection, data

storing, data exchange and data presentation are among key development objectives of UC7.

With regards to the above, one of the most important benefits expected to be achieved by using 5G network is cross-border collaboration of first responders which, in real life, is still faced with many challenges as a consequence of each single PPDR administrative domain operating its own communication system (or, at least incompatible with the cross-border one).

Figure 16: UC7 Service Chain

The UC implementation relies on four AFs and three NFs as specified in Table 52 - Table 55. Initially, 7 AFs and 2 NFs have been foreseen, while one AF and one NF (namely AF#4 - Sensor Awareness Service, and NF#1 - Long-distance communication) turn out not being needed any more in the UC7 due to certain optimizations/modifications done. As well, two AFs have through the development modified from AFs to NFs, i.e., AF#6 -> NF#3 (Cooperative Awareness Service, Table 55) and AF#7 -> NF#4 (Enhanced Local Dynamic Map Service, Table 60). The development of the majority of the functions represents modifications of functions being already available before the beginning of the

project, while a couple of functions are being developed from scratch in order to meet objectives of the UC. All functions have been completed during Cycle A of the project development, while further fine tunings and specific improvements (both in terms of functionality as in terms of integration) will follow during the Cycle B following deviations, issues, etc. identified during testing.

Figure 16 depicts the respective service chain.

2.8.2. AF/NF Development Status

Table 52: AF#1 Monitoring NF

Specification Item	Description – AF#1
NF Name	Monitoring NF
NF Version	1.0
Description	Collecting data from the field (sensors, cameras, cooperative awareness service, etc.) and storing them. Also distributing data (including video streams) to third-party parties, e.g., other AFs.
Deployment	EDGE SERVER+RSU/OBU
Required Resources	CPU: 4x CPU Memory: 8GB RAM Storage: 100GB HDD
Exposed ports	80, 443, 3306, 554 (optional)
Expected Input	HTTP/S MySQL, RTSP (optional)
Expected Output	HTTP/S MySQL, RTSP (optional)
Configuration Options	n/a
Deployment Notes	multi-container deployment
Development Status	Cycle A - Completed

Table 53: AF#2-Analytics NF

Specification Item	Description – AF#2
Name	Analytics NF
Version	1.0

Description	Analytics AF serves for data visualization and reports creation. Data visualization and report structure is based on customer requirements.
Deployment	EDGE SERVER
Required Resources	CPU: 4vCores RAM: >8GB Storage: 20GB
Exposed ports	None
Expected Input	AF#1: HTTPS, MySQL UE: HTTPS
Expected Output	AF#1: HTTPS, MySQL UE: HTTPS
Configuration Options	database URL (regarding AF#1) Grafana URL Management URL
Deployment Notes	n/a
Development Status	Cycle A - Completed

Table 54: AF#3 Streaming NF

Specification Item	Description - AF#3
Name	Streaming NF
Version	1.0
Description	Streaming AF is a video proxy component receiving video stream from cameras and forwarding it to the end users.
Deployment	EDGE SERVER+OBU
Required Resources	CPU: > 2vCores, RAM: > 4GB Storage: >10GB
Exposed ports	554, 80 (optional), 443 (optional)
Expected Input	RTSP
Expected Output	RTSP, webRTC (optional)
Configuration Options	video source URL

Deployment Notes	None
Development Status	Cycle A - Completed

Table 55: AF#5-Simulator of ETSI Cooperative Awareness Service

Specification Item	Description - AF#5
Name	Simulator of ETSI Cooperative Awareness Service
Version	1.0
Description	This AF simulates the same functionalities of the ETSI Cooperative Awareness Basic Service in compliance to standard ETSI EN 302 637-2 V1.4.1.
Deployment	EDGE SERVER+OBU
Required Resources	CPU: < 1 vCPU RAM: < 1GB Storage: < 1GB
Exposed ports	5672 (AMQP 1.0 port) 3000 (REST)
Expected Input	n/a
Expected Output	REST AMQP 1.0
Configuration Options	n/a
Deployment Notes	None
Development Status	Cycle A - Completed

In the UC7, the ITS communication nApp, that is introduced in Section 3.1, is used. In the specific, the NF#3 Cooperative Awareness Basic Service NF is used together with the other NFs of the ITS communication on which it depends on. These other NFs are the Position and Time Service NF, the NF#4 Enhanced Local Dynamic Map Service NF, and the NF#2 Uu C-ITS messages communication NF. The ITS communication nApp is used in the UC7 for sending Cooperative Awareness Messages (CAMs) from the OBU to the edge where the Monitoring AF takes into account the information provided by the CAMS for having a real-time updated situation awareness about the vehicles that are present in the tunnel.

2.8.3. Identified Base nApps

Based on AFs and NFs presented in the Section 2.8.2 , four nApps have been defined (see Table 56). These nApps are considered “standalone”, meaning each of them can be independently used in other UCs and as such available on AOEP platform to be used by third-party party developers. However, besides utilizing 5G network and cloud-continuum infrastructure, nApps are utilizing certain IoT devices which also needs to be considered when being applied in a UC.

Table 56: Base nApps identified in UC7

UC7 Base nApps	ID	Name	Application/Network Functions in nApp	Brief Description
	N-UC7-1	Video stream delivery	AF#1, AF#3, NF#1	Providing a complete end-to-end video streaming service from camera on one end to UE/display on the other end (e.g., UE streams over 5G).
	N-UC7-2	Environmental/IoT monitoring	AF#1, AF#2, NF#1	End-to-end service for collecting any kind of environmental or other data via multiple IoT sensors simultaneously (e.g., temperature, humidity, CO level, etc.), storing, and representing them in multiple ways (processed by statistical methods, raw data; graphical UI, textual – depends on customer/user needs).
	N-UC7-3 ²	Simulator of ETSI Cooperative Awareness Service	NF#5	Simulating presence of multiple vehicles by generating certain vehicle related parameters.
	N-UC7-4	Vehicle monitoring	AF#1, AF#2, AF#6, AF#7, NF#2	Collecting (via OBU), storing, and representing various parameters of the vehicle.

² N-UC7-3 is a highly complex service; therefore, we refer to it as a nApp. N-UC7-3 is composed of some specific atomic components that are wrapped together to hide the complexity to the end user.

3. IDENTIFICATION OF NAPPS

There are several ways to compose a network application, starting from atomic components which are the AFs and NFs, documented and available in the AFs/NFs registry. These available components could be composed (based on their interfaces and documentations) in several ways that could lead to different applications.

Sections 3.1 and 3.2 introduce respectively the ITS communication nApp and the Video Processing nApps. These nApps are two generic nApps that can be used as basis for composing more complex nApps that implement specific automotive services, for instance hazardous notification services. In Sections 2.2-2.8 the nApps provided by the UCs are introduced. Some examples of CCAM-specific nApps design on top of the currently provided nApps are introduced in Section 3.3. Finally, the categorization of the provided nApps towards vertical applicability takes place in section 3.4.

3.1. ITS communication nApp

This nApp implements the functionalities of the ITS communication architecture that is introduced in the ETSI EN 302 665 [4]. The ITS communication is a system that has been defined for communication in the transportation system. The ITS communication system facilitates communication between vehicles (V2V), vehicles and road-side infrastructure (V2I - RSU), and the network infrastructure (edge servers).

The information among the different actors is exchanged using ETSI standardized messages that are named Cooperative-ITS (C-ITS) messages. Several types of messages have been defined to consider different content to be transmitted. For example, Cooperative Awareness Messages (CAMs) are used to send information about the vehicle status (e.g., the position, the dynamics of vehicles), while Decentralized Environmental Notification Messages (DENMs) provide information about hazardous situations and dangers.

The NFs, that are part of this nApp, implement the ITS Facilities Layer, the ITS Access Layer, and the Networking & Transport Layer of the ITS Communication OSI protocol stack as defined in ETSI EN 302 665 [5]. Third-party AFs can be combined with this nApp to exploit the communication functionalities that are offered. The third-party AFs would correspond to the Applications layer of the ITS Communication OSI protocol stack. The NFs, that are constituting the ITS communication nApp, are introduced in the following of this subsection.

3.1.1. Uu C-ITS messages communication

This NF implements the communication of C-ITS messages over the Uu interface. It provides the functionalities of the Access, and the Networking & Transport layers as described in the ETSI EN 302 665 [5]).

This NF follows the same approach used in the 5G-CARMEN project [6] in which communication among vehicles via network (i.e., V2N2V) and between vehicles and the network (i.e., V2N) is performed using the Uu interface. As in the 5G-CARMEN project, AMQP 1.0 is used at the application level. An AMQP 1.0 Message Broker, which is located at the edge server, is used to exchange the C-ITS messages among the different actors involved (e.g., vehicles, roadside and edge server C-ITS applications).

Table 57: Uu C-ITS messages communication NF

Specification Item	Description
Name	Uu C-ITS messages communication
Version	1.0
Deployment Domain	EDGE SERVER+OBU+RSU
Deployment Model	Deployed as a NF within the ITS communication nApp
Required Resources	CPU: 1 vCPU Memory: < 1GB RAM Storage: < 1GB
Exposed ports	5672 (AMQP 1.0 port)
Expected Input	AMQP 1.0
Expected Output	AMQP 1.0
Configuration Options	None
Deployment Notes	This NF deploys an instance of the Uu C-ITS messages communication.

3.1.2. C-ITS Messages Basic Services NFs

These NFs constitute a set of NFs that support AFs for data presentation (i.e., coding and decoding C-ITS messages), and for managing the transmission and the reception of C-ITS messages. They are part of the Facilities layer of the ITS Communication OSI protocol

stack as defined in ETSI EN 302 665 [5], [7], [8] and they are referred to as Basic Services. Each NF is devoted to providing the functionalities for a specific type of C-ITS message. The nApp may include all or only a subset of these NFs.

The following NFs are provided within the context of the 5G-IANA project:

1. Decentralized Environmental Notification Service NF: this NF manages the DENMs according to [7].
2. Cooperative Awareness Basic Service NF: the NF handles the CAMs as defined in [9].
3. Traffic Light Maneuver Service NF: it manages the exchange of information related to traffic light controllers (e.g., traffic light signal state, time before the change to the next state) using Signal Phase And Timing Extended Messages (SPATEMs) [10].
4. Road and Lane Topology Service NF: this NF is in charge to handle the information related to digital maps using management of MAP (topology) Extended Messages (MAPEMs) that provide information about the road topology of specific areas [10].
5. Infrastructure to Vehicle Information Service NF: the management of information related to traffic signs and roadworks warnings is performed by this NF using the Infrastructure to Vehicle Information Messages (IVIMs) [10].
6. Collective Perception Service NF: the Collective Perception Service, that is implemented by this NF, manages the exchange of the environmental information that is gathered from the processing of sensors' data; the information is transferred using Collective Perception Messages (CPMs); the ETSI TR 103 562 [11] [12] introduces the Collective Perception Service; the specification of this basic service (i.e., ETSI TS 103 324) is in approval phase at the time of writing this deliverable and it is not yet public available.
7. Maneuver Coordination Service NF: this NF is in charge to manage the transmission and the reception of the Maneuvers Coordination Messages (MCMs) that are used to convey maneuvers-related information for achieving maneuvers coordination among vehicles; the ETSI TR 103 578 introduces the Maneuver Coordination Service, whereas the specification of this basic service is defined by the ETSI TS 103 561, both documents are not yet public available at the time of writing this deliverable since they are still in draft status.

Table 58: C-ITS Messages Basic Services NFs.

Specification Item	Description
Name	C-ITS Messages Basic Services NFs
Version	1.0

Deployment Model	EDGE SERVER+OBU+RSU
Required Resources	CPU: < 1 Memory: < 1GB RAM Storage: < 1GB
Exposed ports	5672 (AMQP 1.0 port) 3000 (REST)
Expected Input	REST AMQP 1.0
Expected Output	REST AMQP 1.0
Configuration Options	None
Deployment Notes	This NF deploys an instance of one of the C-ITS Messages Basic Services.

3.1.3. Position and Time Service NF

This NF belongs to the Facilities layer. It provides information about the geographical position of the vehicle to the AFs that are instantiated on the vehicle. It provides current time information to the AFs as well. This NF has been implemented according to [8].

Table 59: Position and Time Service NF.

Specification Item	Description
Name	Position and Time Service NF
Version	1.0
Deployment Model	OBU
Required Resources	CPU: < 1 vCPU Memory: < 1GB RAM Storage: < 1GB
Exposed ports	5672 (AMQP 1.0 port) 3000 (REST)

Expected Input	n/a
Expected Output	AMQP 1.0 REST
Configuration Options	None
Deployment Notes	This NF deploys an instance of Position and Time Service.

3.1.4. Enhanced Local Dynamic Map Service NF

This NF implements the Enhanced Local Dynamic Map Service, that is part of the Facilities layer. The NF aims to store information about local events, real-time dynamic object information and information about other road actors (e.g., other vehicles, VRUs) in the surrounding area. It also provides information that has been retrieved from local sensors and from the Collective Perception Service. This NF offers to AFs similar functionalities and interfaces to the ones that are introduced in [13].

Table 60: Enhanced Local Dynamic Map Service NF.

Specification Item	Description
Name	Enhanced Local Dynamic Map Service NF
Version	1.0
Deployment Model	OBU
Required Resources	CPU: 1 vCPU Memory: < 1GB RAM Storage: < 1GB
Exposed ports	3000, 8080 (REST)
Expected Input	REST
Expected Output	REST
Configuration Options	None
Deployment Notes	This NF deploys an instance of Enhanced Local Dynamic Map Service.

3.1.5. Events Relevance Service NF

The relevance of an event for a vehicle is a functionality that is expected to be provided by the Facilities layer of the ITS Communication OSI protocol stack. This NF checks if an event, that is identified by a received DENM, is relevant to the vehicle according to its current location and trajectory and it provides this information as output to the interested AFs.

Table 61: Events Relevance Service NF

Specification Item	Description
Name	Events Relevance Service NF
Version	1.0
Deployment Model	OBU
Required Resources	CPU: < 1 vCPU Memory: < 1GB RAM Storage: < 1GB
Exposed ports	5672 (AMQP 1.0 port) 3000 (REST)
Expected Input	REST AMQP 1.0
Expected Output	REST
Configuration Options	None
Deployment Notes	This NF deploys an instance of Events Relevance Service.

3.2. Video Processing nApp

The Video Processing nApp provides as output the information that is retrieved from the processing of a video stream. Different AFs can be considered depending on this information that needs to be retrieved by the UC in which this nApp is used. For example, this nApp can be made of the “Object detection” AF (Table 4) and a “multi-object tracking” AF for identifying objects in the scene and for tracking their movements. Additional AFs, that can be part of this nApp, may further process the video stream for

retrieving additional information. For example, the nApp can include AFs that perform object volume estimation, or object trajectories prediction.

The nApp can be deployed on edge servers for processing video streams from network-connected cameras or on Road Side Units (RSUs), that are equipped with Graphics Processing Units (GPU) for processing video streams from locally connected cameras.

The Video Processing nApp can be used in several “Hazard notification” UCs. The information provided by the nApp can be exploited by applications that check for hazardous events on the roads. For example, third-party applications can monitor the output data stream of this nApp to check for possible collisions among cars or for unsafe situations related to Vulnerable Road Users (VRUs).

3.3. Examples of CCAM-specific nApps

3.3.1. Collision avoidance service nApp

The schema of a nApp implementing a Collision avoidance service on the OBU side is depicted in Figure 17.

Figure 17: Collision avoidance nApp

In this example, a network-connected camera (i.e., a camera connected to the edge server via a 5G connection or through a wired connection) is available and its video stream is provided in input to the Video Processing nApp that is deployed on the edge server. The Video Processing nApp provides the information about the detected objects to the ITS communication nApp. In this case, the only NFs that are strictly required from the ITS communication nApp are the Collective Perception Service NF, that encodes the objects’ information in standard C-ITS messages, and the C-ITS message Uu communication, that sends the messages to the OBU. Please note that this is not a direct

communication. The NF implements a V2N communication link as detailed in Section 3.1.1. The messages are sent to a Message Broker that is on the edge server and to which the C-ITS messages Uu communication NF, that is running on the OBU, is connected to. On the OBU side, the received messages are decoded from the Collective Perception Service NF and the decoded information is provided to the Collision avoidance AF. This AF, thanks to the knowledge of the current vehicle’s position provided by the Position and Time Service NF, can evaluate which objects are currently relevant and it can detect potential collisions between the vehicle and the present objects.

3.3.2. Queue warning notification service nApp

A Queue warning notification service nApp is depicted in Figure 18.

Figure 18: Queue warning notification service nApp

Similarly, to the Collision avoidance service nApp, a video stream from a network-connected camera is processed by the Video Processing nApp. The retrieved information is provided to a Queue warning event detection AF that monitors possible queue events in that road segment. In the case of dangerous queue events, the AF triggers the generation of an alert message by using the ITS communication nApp. In the specific, the AF sends a DENM generation request to the Decentralized Environmental Notification Service NF. This NF generates and sends DENMs using a V2N communication approach thanks to the C-ITS messages Uu communication NF. On the OBU side, the same communication NF enables the reception of the DENMs that are decoded by the Decentralized Environmental Notification Service NF. The Events Relevance Service exploits the information from the received messages, together with the information of the vehicle’s position provided by the Position and Time Service, to understand if the

signalled event is relevant for the vehicle. In case of relevance, it can provide this information through specific interfaces towards the autonomous driving module or to the HMI if the vehicle is driven by a human.

3.3.3. Speed advice service nApp

Figure 19 illustrates a nApp that provides speed advices to vehicle’s driver.

Figure 19: Speed Advice nApp

On the edge server side, some of the NFs belonging to the ITS communication nApp are used. In the specific, the Traffic Light Maneuver NF receives information from the NF providing an interface with the traffic light controller system, and it forwards the traffic light information to the OBU using the C-ITS messages Uu communication NF. Using the same communication NF, the Road and Lane Topology Service and the Infrastructure to Vehicle Information Service NFs provide respectively the road topology and the speed limits that have been received from the NF that implements an interface with the roadside management system. The same set of NFs, belonging to the ITS communication nApp, are used at the OBU side to receive the messages, to decode and to provide them to a Speed advice AF. This AF, combining the received information together with the position of the OBU provided by the Position and Time Service NF, can compute the optimal speed that the driver should keep.

3.4. Categorization of baseline software components

This section provides a categorization of the nApps showcased in Section 2 towards applicability to a set of verticals defined in:

- Empowering Vertical Industries through 5G Networks - Current Status and Future Trends. [14]
- the vertical's cartography, where the 5G related UC experiments that are taking place in Europe is being tracked. [12]

A total of 23 nAPPs have been identified for the purposes of 5G-IANA UCs, a mapping of the 5G network services towards the 5G vertical industries can be found in Table 62. The verticals most supported by the provided network services are Automotive, Transport & logistics, Smart Cities & Utilities Public Safety and Media & entertainment.

Table 62: 5G-IANA baseline software components categorization

nApp/ Vertical	Indu stry 4.0	Agricu lture & Agri- food	Auto- motive	Trans p-ort & logi- stics	Smart Cities & utilitie s	Public Safety	Smart air- ports	Energy	eHealt h & well- ness	Media & entert ainme nt	Vertic al Agno- stic
Total:	4	0	14	5	3	4	1	0	0	6	4
Real Time Stream Delivery	x		x							x	
Object Detection Stream and Data Delivery	x		x								
AGV Data Processing, Communication and Control	x		x	x							
Remote Driving			x								
MCAD Edge Node			x	x	x	x					
MCAD Rover Node			x	x	x	x					
AI Enhanced Video Stream Delivery										x	
Video enabled VR Client										x	

Active Network Monitoring Module											x
Virtual Bus Tour - UC3										x	
AR App										x	
AR streaming application										x	
Real-time Hazardous driving event detection			x								
Aggregated Hazardous driving event detection			x								
Real-time vehicle trajectory prediction			x								
Hazardous driving event notification - UC5			x								
Predictive QoS			x	x			x				
Obtain Training Data											x
DML Training											x
Video stream delivery											x
Environmental/IoT monitoring	x		x	x	x	x					
Simulator of ETSI Cooperative			x								

Awareness Service											
Vehicle monitoring			x			x					

4. PROGRESS TOWARDS INTEGRATION OF THE NAPPS WITH THE 5G-IANA PLATFORM

This section contains initially a high-level presentation of approaches used by other relevant European projects to store and deploy nApps. Then the onboarding process to the AOEP and the onboarding API is discussed.

4.1. Common approaches by other ICT-41 project on nApp storage and deployment

The following section, aims to present the different approaches used by projects for 5G-PPP – 5G innovations for verticals with third-party services (ICT-41) to store their nApps and make them available for use and deployment. The presentation is kept on a high-level on purpose, as its focus is not to explain the underlying technologies but offer an overview of the functionalities offered by other projects in comparison with the functionalities showcased in the remainder of this section. The intended audience is third-party experimenters; however, this information can be of value to any vertical intending to deploy its applications in a form of an nApp.

4.1.1. Common approaches on nApp repositories

The various European projects belonging in the ICT-41 call have adapted multiple approaches to store their nApps and make them available for use by various verticals. Smart5Grid proposes the Open Service Repository [15], part of the Smart5Grid platform that can store the subcomponents of nApps i.e., applications served as Network Services (NSs), NFs, Virtual Deployment Units (VDUs), and images. It follows a detailed data model and utilizes CI/CD methods.

The VITAL-5G Open Online Repository [16] is an essential element of the VITAL-5G Platform, serving as a platform for the collection of nApps developed for the project. It offers the opportunity for third-party experimenters and developers to download and choose nApps for experimentation, as well as to incorporate their own nApps to create new vertical services. The repository consists of three primary catalogues that enable users to search and incorporate nApp packages, Vertical Service Blueprints, and Descriptors, along with Experiment Blueprints and Descriptors. These catalogues also include associated NF packages and NFV Network Service Descriptors [17].

The 5G Induce project [18] introduces the NAO (NetApp Orchestration) layer, which functions as a container registry for vertical AFs and facilitates their deployment. Additionally, a component called the "Shared Repository" establishes a connection between the NAO operator and the 5G telco administrative domains. The Shared Repository serves as a shared catalogue between the NAO operator and the MNO, containing metadata of all supported NFs that can potentially be deployed within a slice. Within the 5G-MEDIA HUB [19], an nApp Repository application exists, primarily designed to facilitate the onboarding of nApps onto the underlying 5G testbeds. This application enables users to design, validate, and deploy their nApps based on the available NFs listed in the service catalogue. The underlying 5G testbeds offer features such as Catalogue Management and Service Ordering, allowing users to design nApps through a "drag and drop" interface, where NFs can be placed on a canvas and interconnected to create forwarding graphs.

In the context of 5GASP [20], a nApp Marketplace has been established, serving as a public registry for SMEs and their registered products. It includes reusable nApps, Network Function (NF) and Network Service (NS) links to open-source repositories, and informative documentation to assist SMEs in understanding and implementing a certification process. The nApp Marketplace is complemented by a nApp community that provides support for third-party development.

Another notable approach is implemented by the EVOLVED-5G [21] project. Their nApp repository consists of two distinct components. Firstly, they utilize GitHub as a platform to generate the nApp file structure using a predefined template within their Software Development Kit (SDK) toolchain. Developers can share their nApp code on this repository. Secondly, the Open Repository is employed to store and manage all nApp images (binaries). This Open Repository acts as an extension to other repositories like GitHub, which typically serve as source code repositories. During the validation and certification stages, the Repository will be connected to a third workspace component, enabling a continuous integration and continuous deployment (CI/CD) lifecycle.

Finally, 5G-Epicentre refers to a Network Service repository [22] which handles the lifecycle of NF/CNF via the utilization of Helm Charts, however no additional details are provided in the public deliverables of the project.

4.1.2. Common approaches on vertical service integration

Based on the related literature, the approaches presented for the integration of nApps can be distinguished in three different categories [4], based in their position in the architecture of each system and the ensuing interactions. These approaches are named a) coupled or delegated, b) As-a-Service and c) Hybrid approach. nApps can either be exposed as a service to vertical applications using APIs, or be integrated within a vertical application or finally an approach which combines the two first can be used. In the delegated approach, the nApp owner delegates the nApp to the telco operator i.e., the owner provides the nApp and the telco operator is responsible for deploying and operating it in their domain. In this approach, the nApp can be considered a part of the 5G system. In the “As-a-Service” approach, the nApp is adjacent to the 5G system and the telco domain. The nApp is provided to the vertical application as a service via APIs, while the vertical deploys his/her application in the so-called Vertical Service provider domain. Finally, the third approach, also utilized in 5G-IANA, is called Hybrid, where parts of the Vertical Service are deployed in the vertical domain while parts of the Vertical Service are instantiated in the operator domain, e.g., in an Edge Server. These three categories are depicted in Figure 20. The most commonly used category in the context of H2020 research project, is the “As a Service” followed by the Hybrid approach as seen in Table 63.

Figure 20: Categorization of nApps, based on the integration approach, based on [23]

Table 63: Approaches on vertical service integration used in relevant H2020 programs

Project	As a Service Approach	Hybrid Approach	Coupled / Delegated Approach
5G IANA		✓	
5G ERA [24]	✓		
Affordable 5G [25]			✓
DAEMON [26]	✓	✓	
Teraflow [27]	✓		
5G Epicentre [28]	✓	✓	
5G INDUCE [18]		✓	
Smart5Grid [29]			✓
5GASP [20]	✓	✓	✓

5GMediaHUB [30]	✓		
Evolved-5G [31]	✓		✓
Vital 5G [32]	✓		
5G-Victori [33]	✓		

* Affordable5G uses xAPPs, a variant of nApps specific the O-RAN approach

4.2. 5G-IANA platform onboarding process

After developing a network application using either the nApp starter kit or self-deployed components, it can be added to the 5G-IANA catalogue available on the platform. This allows developers to manage, monitor, and test their applications using the platform’s tools and the 5G-IANA testbed environment. This functionality has the potential to support the creation of reliable and highly functional network applications for the automotive industry, benefiting both end-users and businesses.

Third-party developers have the option to utilize the 5G-IANA platform and some of the network applications developed within the project to design, develop, and test new network applications for the automotive sector. The platform can be especially advantageous for developing and deploying network applications that utilize the nApp starter kit as a software foundation.

Specifically, the 5G-IANA platform offers a public Git repository where the nApp starter kits and related software documentation are distributed. These resources can serve as a starting point for third-party developers when creating their own network applications. Some starter kits provide open-source software components that can be customized and expanded as needed, while others provide proprietary software components (such as libraries or stand-alone applications with open interfaces) that can be integrated with external third-party software to build new applications.

The table below presents the available nApp starter kits categorized based on the services and functionalities they offer. A nApp developer can access these kits from the public Git repository and use them as a foundation to create a completely new network application. Detailed documentation on how to use each network application and its components is stored in a dedicated folder within the Git repository, as explained in the following section.

The structure of a nApp repository is illustrated in [34] and reported in Figure 21.

```
-  
- *blueprint.json  
- license/  
- documentation/  
- test/
```

Figure 21: nApp repository structure

The structure of the nApp includes the blueprint. JSON template and three optional folders that contain the licenses for the network application and its components, documentation on how to use it, and potentially provided tests within the starter kit. The blueprint template is necessary for using the nApp and is organized as follows:

```
{  
  "netAppPackageId": "UUID autogenerated",  
  "name": "string",  
  "description": "string",  
  "version": "string",  
  "type": [SERVICE, COMPONENT],  
  "serviceCategory": [HAZARD_NOTIFICATION, VEHICLE_MOVEMENT, SMART_TRAFFIC_PLANNING, INFOTAINMENT],  
  "servicePackageURL": "string",  
  "packageType": [HELM, ...],  
  "specLevel": [VERTICAL_AGNOSTIC, VERTICAL_SPECIFIC],  
  "accessLevel": [PRIVATE, RESTRICTED, PUBLIC],  
  "useCase": "string",  
  "testbed": [NOKIA, TS],  
  "atomicComponents": [],  
  "requiredEquipment": [],  
  "providedInterfaceSpec": [],  
  "softwareLicenses" : []  
}
```

Figure 22: nApp template

A network application developer can utilize the nApp starter kit templates to create their own network application. They have the option to use the pre-existing components within the templates or implement their own component. If they choose to implement their own component, it needs to be containerized and included in the atomicComponents section of the template. To ensure compatibility with the 5G-IANA platform, the new application components must be delivered as container images that can be managed under the Kubernetes framework.

The nApp template is automatically generated by the 5G-IANA Graphical composer. However, the nApp developer can also manually create the template by following the structure shown in Figure 22. The atomicComponents section is where all the information about each component in the network application is stored, including the image to use, the exposed interfaces, and the connections with other components.

The provided Interface Spec and software Licenses sections contain references to the documentation and software licenses included in the nApp package. The required Equipment section is used to list all the necessary equipment for running the nApp.

Once the nApp developer has filled the nApp template to create their network application, they can onboard the template on the nApp toolkit using a REST API (described in Section 4.3). This onboarding process will validate the template and retrieve all the information of the network application required for deployment by the orchestrator.

Additionally, third parties have the capability to utilize existing network applications from the catalogue and modify them using the Vertical App Composition & Customization tool.

4.3. Onboarding REST API

The onboarding REST API is the following:

```
http://192.168.100.1:8082/portal/catalogue/netapppackages
```

Figure 23: Onboarding REST API

With a Request Body Parameter, that is sent within the request body and it is used to send complex data or larger payloads.

The Request Body should be the .zip file containing the blueprint.json and the nApp license, documentation and test folders as defined in Figure 21).The API responses are the following:

```
@ApiResponse(code = 201, message = "Onboarded a new NetApp packageits ID.", response = UUID.class),
@ApiResponse(code = 400, message = "The request contains elementsimpossible to process", response = ResponseEntity.class),
@ApiResponse(code = 409, message = "There is a conflict with the request", response = ResponseEntity.class),
@ApiResponse(code = 500, message = "Status 500", response = ResponseEntity.class)
```

Figure 24: Onboarding REST API response

After the Onboarding REST API is successfully executed, on the nApp catalogue will be available the nApp just onboarded.

The onboarded nApp blueprint is stored in the PostgreSQL database of the nApp catalogue and the licenses, the documents and the testcases are stored on the nApp catalogue MiNio filesystem [35].

5. CONCLUSIONS

In this document we present the current status of the 5G-IANA Vertical services, nApps, developed for the purposes of the UCs, along with the ITS and Video processing nApps that are supplied.

In Section 2.1 the uniform reporting template which is used by all nApps is introduced. The relationship to the information model presented in D4.1 and the GUI of the AOEP is discussed. Sections 2.2-2.8 provide the current status of all UCs, explaining the dependencies between each atomic software component that composes the UCs' service chain. Details on the status, interfaces and configuration options of each atomic component is provided. Additionally, the nApps which were identified in each UC are explained.

Section 3 follows the same procedure for the ITS communication (3.1) and Video processing nApps (3.2). The atomic components composing the aforementioned nApps are being utilized to enhance the UCs of 5G-IANA. Furthermore, in Section 3.3 examples of CCAM nApps, which could be developed, serving as an exploitation point for the AOEP's third-party party experimenters. Finally, in Section 3.4 a categorization of the UC nApps towards other verticals is provided.

In section 4, the integration progress towards the platform is presented. Initially a literature review of the other ICT-41 projects in regards to verticals with third-party services to store and deploy their vertical services and make them available for use and deployment is demonstrated in Section 4.1. In Sections 4.2, 4.3 the onboarding process and the onboarding API, which are utilized to onboard the nApps to the AOEP are supplied.

The next step involves the integration and deployment of the described Vertical services to the AOEP and exploitation of the testbeds' 5G services. Moreover, the development, deployment and integration of Cycle B components will be reported in D4.3 - Final report on intelligent nApps and 5G-IANA UCs development and integration, which will be provided in M36.

ANNEX I: GRAPHICAL REPRESENTATION OF NAPPS PER UC

Figure 25: UC1 nApp - Real Time Stream Delivery (N-UC1-1) - Table 11.

Figure 26: UC1 nApp – Object Detection Stream and Data Delivery (N-UC1-2) - Table 11.

Figure 27: UC1 nApp – AGV Data Processing, Communication and Control (N-UC1-3) - Table 11.

Figure 28: UC2 nApp - MCAD roover node (N-UC2-1) - Table 18

Figure 29: UC2 nApp - MCAD edge node (N-UC2-2) - Table 18.

Figure 30: UC3 nApp - AI Enhanced Video Stream Delivery (N-UC3-1) - Table 32.

Figure 31: UC3 nApp - Video Enabled VR client (N-UC3-2) - Table 32.

Figure 32: UC3 nApp – Active Network Monitoring Module (N-UC3-3) - Table 32.

Figure 33: UC4 nApp – AR streaming application (N-UC4-2) - Table 39.

Figure 34: UC5 nApp – Real-time Hazardous driving event detection (N-UC5-1) - Table 44.

Figure 35: UC5 nApp – Aggregated Hazardous driving event detection (N-UC5-2) - Table 44.

Figure 36: UC5 nApp – Real-time vehicle trajectory prediction (N-UC5-3) - Table 44.

Figure 37: UC5 nApp - Hazardous driving event notification (N-UC5-4) - Table 44.

Figure 38: UC6 nApp – Predictive QoS (N-UC6-1) - Table 51.

Figure 39: UC6 nApp – Obtain Training Data (N-UC6-2) - Table 51.

Figure 40: UC6 nApp – DML Training (N-UC6-3) - Table 51.

Figure 41: UC7 nApp - Video Stream Delivery (N-UC7-1) - Table 56.

Figure 42: UC7 nApp - Environmental monitoring (N-UC7-2) - Table 56.

Figure 43: UC7 nApp – Simulator of ETSI Cooperative Awareness Service (N-UC7-3) - Table 56.

Figure 44: UC7 nApp – Vehicle Monitoring (N-UC7-4) - Table 56.

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